

Caroline Pratt's Do-With Toys™ and Unit Blocks

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Abstract

This study sketches the early history of Caroline Pratt's Do-With Toys™ and her Unit Blocks.

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Introduction

The 1913 Holiday Number of the *New York Times Review of Books* has a small but interesting newspaper ad by the Child-Lore Book Room (1913):

Christmas Gifts. Child-Lore Book Room, John Martin's House. Rooms full of the best books for children and many "Do-with" toys.

In fact, the actual Child-Lore Book Room was not located in John Martin's House at all, but in 47th Street, not far from Fifth Avenue, New York City. The Book Room was the outcome of an initiative of Josephine Emerson, Principal of the Open-Air School for Girls and Boys, a private school for children between ages four and twelve (Sargent, 1924, p. 295). In the early 1910s, Miss Emerson established a circulating library at the school. Consequently, in 1913, she organized the aforementioned Christmas book exhibit. The John Martin's House was the publisher's HQ in 30th Street of the *John Martin's Book* magazine for children aged four to ten. Next, in 1914, Miss Emerson's school opened the Child-Lore Book Room — a separate bookshop to sell books to children of the well off. In 1917, the bookshop moved with the school from 47th Street to 64th Street where Miss Emerson already arranged a Christmas book exhibit that same year (*Publisher's Weekly*, 1917; Elser, 1917). Note that the bookshop was still listed in the 1922 edition of the *American Book Trade Manual*, so it survived both the war years and the aftermath of WWI.

Now, what is truly interesting about the small newspaper ad, quoted above, is *not* so much the message that the exhibit rooms were filled with books, but that there were many Do-With™ toys too (see *Figure 1* and *Figure 2*). Since 1908, Caroline Pratt (see *Figure 3* and *Figure 4*) manufactured these jointed wooden Do-With™ dolls and other toys — trademarked in 1911. She also produced building blocks. Just a few months before the 1913 Child-Lore Book Room Christmas Exhibit was held, Pratt had co-founded Play School (later renamed City and Country School) in New York's Greenwich Village together with Edna Smith (see *Note 1* and *Figure 10*). And, as of 1917, Pratt wanted to manufacture wooden "Little World Dolls," but this dream of hers never came true (*C&C100. Newsletter for Alumni, Parents, and Friends*, 2014/2015; Clarke et al., 2015; Staring, 2013b).

Caroline Louise Pratt

During her life, Caroline Pratt has taken many forms: for instance, as a primary school teacher, as a kindergarten teacher, as a researcher, as a settlement worker, as a Socialist (e.g., Pratt, 1912a), as a book writer and author of many articles on early childhood education — but also as a book reviewer (e.g., Pratt, 1925a-b, 1950). During her later life she was best known as Principal of City and Country School and for her Unit Blocks (e.g., *Life*, 1945).

Who was Caroline Pratt in 1908 when she began producing wooden dolls and toys?

Caroline Louise Pratt, born on May 13, 1867 in Fayetteville, New York was the third child of Lydia C. (Rowley) Pratt and Henry S. Pratt. She had her first teaching experience in 1884 after having applied for the position of teacher for the summer session at a school near Pompey, not far from Fayetteville. In 1886, Pratt took the Regents' Advanced Examination; a year later she was appointed an assistant teacher in the Primary Department of the Fayetteville village school. Then, in 1892, after having obtained a scholarship, she began her classes in the College for the Training of Teachers (later renamed Teachers College) professional diploma course in kindergarten methods at 9 University Place, near Washington Square, New York City. She later wrote in her autobiography *I Learn From Children* (three printings in 1948) that she soon switched to Manual Training — or Arts and Crafts, as it was known at the time.

My first act of rebellion, then, was to go to the Dean and announce that Kindergarten was not for me. Guessing rightly that country living had given me a capable pair of hands, he suggested Arts and Crafts. (Pratt, 1948a, p. 15; 1948b, p. 15; compare Kurriger, 1973).

After receiving her diploma in 1894, she moved to Philadelphia, Pennsylvania where she taught Woodworking at the Normal School for Girls until 1901. Interestingly, the *School Journal* (1895) already portrayed her early teaching practice. A year later the *Journal of Education* (1896) reported that Pratt's Principal George H. Cliff had placed her in special charge of the "study of carpentry, or the training in sloyd... The equipment is complete, the training skilful, the effect upon the girls' physical, intellectual, and professional life noticeable." That year, Pratt attended a summer course in the Sloyd (*Slöjd*) instruction of woodworking at Naas (*Nääs*), Sweden. Yet, from 'Manual Training at Nääs,' a report Pratt (1901) published half a decade later, we may deduce she did not really enjoy both the method and her tutors (for critique on Pratt's article, consult Craig, 1901; Johnson, 1921; Thorbjörnsson, 2006). Next, in 1897, Pratt attended special courses for teachers in Philadelphia. Charles Hanford Henderson's lectures about Organic Education inspired her. Although Pratt (1948a) wrote in her autobiography that Henderson "had stirred up [her] thinking" (p. 57), and even though she likely had read his *Education and the Larger Life* (1902), she never became as enthusiastic about his approach to manual training and education in general as others did — like for example Marietta L. Johnson who in 1907 founded the School of Organic Education in Fairhope, Alabama (Staring, 2013b, 2014, 2016).

In 1901, Pratt began part-time work for the College Settlement of Philadelphia, but in the fall of that year she moved to New York City where she began teaching carpentry and manual training at a settlement house (name unknown), at a private school (name unknown), and at Hartley House — Hell's Kitchen's social settlement house. Apart from a small number of articles that were politically inspired, Pratt (1902a-b, 1905) also published about her work as a teacher at Hartley House (Staring, 2013b, 2015). *Hartley House News*, the newsletter put together by children during printing classes, regularly reported about the popularity of her carpentry classes. In 1902, the number of her classes had already grown from two to nine. Pratt also regularly informed colleague settlement workers about her work. On March 6, 1903, for instance, she delivered an address on carpentry at the practical conference of the Association of Neighborhood Workers, held at the School of Ethical Culture, New York City. Pratt's work consisted of these three jobs until the fall of 1908. Pratt biographer Carlton (1986, p. 169) quotes the November 18, 1908 *Hartley House News* in which the dismissal of Pratt is mentioned — a resignation at the request of Pratt, because she wanted to become more active as a member of the Socialist Party and within the Women's Trade Union League. Furthermore, she planned to market wooden toys and dolls she was designing at the time.

Caroline Pratt's Do-With Toys™

The *New York Times Review of Books* advertisement, quoted in the Introduction above, is one of the indications that Caroline Pratt's toys and dolls were well known amongst early childhood educators in 1913. Pratt had first demonstrated them at the 1909 Annual General Meeting of the International Kindergarten Union, held in Buffalo, New York. *Kindergarten Review* (1909a) reported, "Miss Pratt, a manual training teacher at New York, presented a full exhibit of her new 'Do-With' toys." And *Kindergarten-Primary Magazine* (1909) wrote, "Some quaint looking animals made of wood in proportion to their sizes, invented by miss Pratt, teacher of manual training in New York, were exhibited." Later that year, Pratt placed advertisements, for instance in the weekly opinion magazine *The Outlook* (Pratt, 1909d; see *Figure 5*) and in

The Craftsman — the monthly magazine of the American branch of the Arts and Crafts movement (Pratt, 1909a-c).

On November 6, 1909, the *Evening Post* (1909b) published ‘Toys That Help The Child,’ the first newspaper article that describes Pratt’s Do-With™ toys. Three kinds of toys were listed, the first two favoured by adults, the third by children:

- (i) ‘Do-Nothings.’ Toys that do nothing by themselves and are not funny to play with;
- (ii) ‘Look-Ons.’ Mechanical toys that do all the playing by themselves after having been winding up;
- (iii) “Do-Withs,” or “toys for the do-with children.” These “seem to be inviting you to come and play with them,” are wooden dolls (men, women and children) and animals (horses, cows, sheep, calves, pigs and dogs), houses and stables, chairs, sofas and tables, carts, and, lastly, furniture “after the fashions of [Thomas] Chippendale.”

Figure 1: Original artistic drawing of wooden Do-With™ horse and cart, circa 1908, by Caroline Pratt (left). Figure 2: Original artistic drawing of wooden, jointed, Do-With™ doll, circa 1908, by Caroline Pratt (right). In 1910, the *New York Daily Tribune* (1910a) published photos of these drawings. (Photos: Jeroen Staring, 2011. Courtesy City and Country School, New York City).

The *Evening Post* (1909b) article further stated,

The toys may be bought one or a few at a time, but each is part of a scheme, and with them all or even with several the child may work out systems of play that will inspire it mentally, perhaps, in something of the manner which Froebel found so successful in his “gifts.”...In making the toys no effort has been made to “particularize,” as it were, but essential characteristics are emphasized and the rest left to the child’s imagination...They are all strongly made of wood, generally in threeply, are strong, and are in excellent color and proportion.

Two weeks later, the *Evening Post* article was reprinted in the *Washington Herald* (1909).

Advertisements in *Evening Telegram* and *Evening World* reveal that Do-With™ toys were available in 1910 on the fourth floor of Gimbel Brothers, Corner Broadway and 32nd Street, New York City (Gimble Brothers, 1910a-b). The ads state,

The “Do-With” Toys Sold Exclusively By Gimbels. For the little boy who voiced the protest of childhood that toys “just played by themselves” the “Do-With” toys were created, and the child-heart is now delighted with toys which can make play with him.

Here are the farmer and his wife, his boy and girl, his horse and wagon, his cows, his calves, his colts, his dogs — the “Do-With” horses that can be harnessed to “Do-With” wagons, “Do-With” ponies, which the child can ride, and all other members of the usual domestic menagerie to afford unending amusement.

New York Daily Tribune (1910a) stated too that Pratt began to produce toys after a boy had told her that he was not fond of his mechanical toys because they play *for* him, not *with* him. The article was later reprinted in *Christian Science Monitor* (1910) and *Miami Metropolis* (1910), and in summarized form in *Detroit Free Press* (1910).

New York Herald (1910a) published an illustrated article, titled ‘The Birth Of The Do-With Toy,’ subtitled, ‘One Rebellion by One Child Provides an Idea for a Clever Woman and a New Scheme of Playthings Is the result.’ Its first paragraph re-tells the *New York Daily Tribune* (1910a) story that Pratt

began her toys venture after a boy had told her he wanted toys “he could make play with him” and definitely *not* toys that play by themselves. Subsequent paragraphs declare that Pratt investigated toys available in Europe and in the United States, but found them wanting — categorized into either toy that looks pretty and does nothing, or mechanical toys that play by themselves. These toys, before long, cease to be appealing to children. According to the *New York Herald* (1910a), Pratt first created various members of Do-With™ families (women, men, girls, boys) before she started producing various wooden animals, carts, houses, stables, and furniture. The *New York Herald* journalist further stated,

The Toy designer, who is Miss Caroline Pratt, is only starting on her career and profession. The “Do-Withs” are still in their infancy, and at present they are all born in Greenwich Village, where Miss Pratt presides over a small workshop...Miss Pratt’s toys have the approval of many kindergarten experts in this city and elsewhere. Miss Patty S. Hill, Head of the kindergarten department at Teachers’ College, recommends them for children’s toys, and they are used at the Ethical Culture School in kindergarten work. Miss M. B. B. Langzettel, of the Froebel Kindergarten and Teachers’ College, is a firm believer in the successful future of the “Do With” toys. Miss Pratt will have charge of the toy shop in the Child Welfare Exhibition, which will be held [in New York City] in January [1911].

Note that sections in the *New York Herald* (1910a) article are virtually identical to paragraphs in *Evening Post* (1909b), *Washington Herald* (1909), as well as in *New York Daily Tribune* (1910a), mentioned above. An article in the *San Francisco Call* (1911) has identical sections too. Besides, two of six photographs illustrating the *New York Herald* (1910a) article also appeared in *San Francisco Call* (1911). It is therefore very likely that journalists made use of a handout, or press kit, written by Pratt herself.

1911: Child Welfare Exhibit, New York City and Chicago

As announced in the *New York Herald* (1910a), Pratt demonstrated her wooden Do-With™ toys in the winter and spring of 1911, first at the Child Welfare Exhibit in New York City, in the 71st Regiment Armory (January 18 to February 12), and three months later at the Child Welfare Exhibit in Chicago, in the Coliseum (May 11 to May 12).

Pratt was on the NYC exhibit’s Sub Committee on Home Life. The *Handbook of the New York Child Welfare Exhibit* explicitly refers to her Do-With™ dolls and toys as well as to her activities as an expert demonstrator during the exhibit.

Because play is the first need of children, the living room will give prominence to a child’s corner, with a home-made doll’s house and other things for the child’s use. The child’s room will contain a home-made work-bench and certain recommended toys, some of which are of the “do with” type. Near the model rooms, will be a toy shop in which the right kind of toys will be exhibited. By the toy shop door a work-bench will be located and here experts will give demonstrations of the proper use of toys and, on different days, will actually make many of the toys shown inside the shop. (New York Child Welfare Committee, 1911, p. 24).

Another subdivision in this *Handbook* refers to the exhibit’s ‘Play Shop’ and to three so-called tests that should be applied to toys. These tests — that is, “playability,” “artistic quality,” and “toy making” tests (p. 25) — positively indicate three out of four qualities of Do-With™ toys listed in Pratt’s 1909 *Craftsman* advertisements: “Do-withs are Playable,..., Makeable, Artistic” (Pratt 1909a-c). The handbook of the Chicago Child Welfare Exhibit paid attention to Pratt’s toys too, in very similar texts (Chicago Child Welfare Exhibit, 1911, pp. 21-22), and it had a photo of the ‘toy shop,’ or ‘Play Shop’ (p. 23; see *Figure 6*). In “Toys: A Usurped Educational Field,” an article that describes her own experiences at the Child Welfare Exhibit, issued in the *Survey* as well as in the *Reform Advocate*, Pratt would later that year state that she was in favour of toys as manufactured by herself, “to satisfy the demands of playability...make-ability, and of artistic merit” (Pratt, 1911b, p. 893; 1911c, p. 283).

Figure 3: Caroline Pratt. Part of the larger photo on December 4, 1910, *New York Herald* (left). Figure 4: Caroline Pratt. The photo on December 4, 1910, *New York Herald* (right).

A few months prior to the New York Child Welfare Exhibit, publications in *Brooklyn Daily Eagle* (1910), *New York Daily Tribune* (1910b) and *New York Herald* (1910a-c) already announced Pratt's Play Shop. Several of these articles declared that Santa Claus has a right to the degree of Doctor of Pedagogy. *New York Herald* (1910b) explained,

To prove his right, the home section of the exhibit is to show a toy shop, not in charge of mere clerks, but actually operated by fascinating toy makers. And before the eyes of the little ones who peer through the low shop window or cluster around the busy toy makers at work on a bench in Toy Street, wonderful treasures are to grow from wood, cloth paper, bits of wire, paste and paints. Three toy specialists, Miss Caroline B. [sic] Pratt, the "Do-With" toy expert, Paty [sic] S. Hill, professor of the kinderparten [sic] department, Teachers' College, and Miss Louise Brigham, the box furniture expert, are to be the toy makers and managers. From time to time, children will also serve as toy makers.

There are many Toys for Grown-ups
[They are the Look-ons]
DO-WITH TOYS are for CHILDREN
[They can do things with them. That's what children like.]
The family of Do-Withs (50c. each, including pattern for clothes and postage) can sit and stand. They are fully jointed, unbreakable wooden dolls. Send for father, mother (8 inches), girl or boy (6 inches) doll and catalogue of **Farm Stock** and **Carts** of the Do-With Family to
C. PRATT, 341 4th Ave., New York City, or inquire of your best art store or craft shop.

Figure 5: Advertisement on November 20, 1909, *Outlook* (Pratt, 1909d).

Brooklyn Daily Eagle (1910) had a similar explanation, with identical misspellings. Two-and-a-half weeks prior to the opening of the Exhibit, the *San Francisco Call* (1911) published an illustrated article about Do-With™ toys and dolls. The newspaper narrated the story of the boy who complained about his mechanical toys, in effect leading to, or instigating, the designing of the Do-With™ doll family, farm animal toys, house, furniture, and barn. This time, Pratt was portrayed as *the boy's aunt* who before starting to design her own toys had inspected every toy from America and Europe. The article further focused on Pratt's view that dolls and toys should possess proper relative proportions. Pratt concluded the interview by indicating that she had made patterns for the dolls, "so that more clothes can be made if the child has a fancy for sewing." Note that Pratt's (1909d) *Outlook* advertisement also indicated that patterns for clothes for the Do-With™ dolls were available; see *Figure 5*.

Figure 6: New York Child Welfare Exhibit Play Shop in the July 1911 *Life and Labor* (O'Reilly, 1911).

Evening World published a nicely illustrated article about the New York Child Welfare Exhibit (see *Figure 7*). Ethel Lloyd Patterson (1911), the article's author, paid well attention to Pratt's Do-With™ toys. She stated, "The toys, including the 'Dowiths,' have all been approved by experts and are on exhibition to demonstrate the ethical and educational values of properly selected playthings." Patterson had interviewed Miss Agatha Kent, who was in charge of the exhibit's Play Shop. Kent explained that toy experts strongly disapproved of mechanical toys. They encouraged children to make their own toys. She showed a so-called 'Dowith tray,' containing a pair of scissors with rounded points, crayons, a box of paints, a pencil, and other implements and a basin in which to mix the paints. She spelled out, "With these tools any child ought to be able to construct toys. Miss Pratt is the originator of the Dowith tray and the Dowith playthings." Kent further clarified Pratt's views about encouraging children's curiosity, activity, thinking and learning.

The idea of properly selected toys is to encourage the child to think for itself...One way is to give the child...a pair of scissors. Then the child must be encouraged to think what he needs to complete his toy. Is it paper to cut with the scissors? Plainly he should be able to reason that a pair of scissors is not amusing unless there is something to cut; and so he is taught to play and to think at the same time.

New York Times (1911) had an article about the New York Child Welfare Exhibit as well. It mentions Pratt's toys:

There was a particularly large group [of visitors] drawn up in front of one booth where the "Do With" family of jointed wooden dollies were going through their daily exercises to edify the children in charge of them.

And the socialist newspaper *New York Call* published 'The Strange Child Goes To The Welfare Exhibit,' a rather silly story about a boy who visited the exhibit, and who found the information given disappointing. The story's author, Member of the Heterodoxy Club, social worker and journalist Grace Potter (1911) wrote about the Exhibit's toys department:

"Better for the child to have these crude toys which typify the savage time of development in racial constructiveness. No, little boy, you can't take it away. No, I am sorry. You must leave it for other children to see and their papas and mammas. "I—like—it—so," began the child hoarsely. But it was taken gently from his arms.

Figure 7: Excerpt from Patterson's (1911) *Evening World* article.

In a letter to the Editor, member of the Socialist Party Caroline Pratt (1911a) replied to Potter's daftness in the *New York Call*. She categorized the story "a scathing arraignment." Pratt criticized the article by "Comrade Potter;" her letter sketches her view that the "accomplishment in the future will be largely along the lines of giving to those people who have become experts in education under capitalism and to their successors the opportunity to carry out their ideas under Socialism." Pratt hoped for a feasible socialist Utopia in education. "The more we, as Socialists, take this attitude toward what should be conserved under the present educational system and the theories back of it, reserving our criticism for that which deserves it, the less work shall we have to do when we come into real power."

Brooklyn Daily Eagle (1911) had a report on the New York Child Welfare Exhibit in their children's section; the article described a playroom "fitted up with box furniture — all home-made," "a home-made doll's house, a home-made workbench and other home-made toys," and noted that adults were "beginning to realize that play is the first need of children." The article also stated that in the Play Shop in the special Exhibit's 'Child's Corner' there were all sorts of toys. Manual training students showed what was being taught at their school "by real work by a class at a bench."

All these newspaper articles show that Pratt's Do-With™ toys made a substantial impression on the New York City exhibit's visitors. An interview with Pratt, first published on June 1, 1911 — that is, almost three weeks after the Chicago Child Welfare Exhibit — in the *Whitesville News* (1911) was reprinted in at least twelve other newspapers between June 2 and August 10, e.g., in the *Castilian*, *Dakota County Herald*, *Herald-Advance*, *Corbett's Herald*, *Daily Enquirer*, *Celina Democrat*, *North Platte Semi-Weekly Tribune*, *Sheboygan Daily Express*, *Oelwein Daily Register*, *Virginia Enterprise*, *Evening Telegram*, and the *Wauheshia Freeman* respectively, and perhaps even in more newspapers, in more States.

Pratt told the journalist,

"A 'do with' toy is one that will teach the child how to do things. With it a boy or girls [*sic*] can carry out definite play schemes. It should be simple. It teaches the child by stimulating its imaginative nature and inventive faculties. Such features are lost altogether in the elaborate mechanical toys that leave nothing for the child to do but press a button or release a catch and watch it go."

And,

"What we are trying to do through our exhibit is to teach parents that their children have a normal play impulse which can be more easily gratified with a few simple toys that tend to inspire the child's imagination and inventive nature than by all the complicated and mechanical toys in the world."

Articles mentioning Pratt's toys were published in magazines as well, e.g., the Women's Trade Union League magazine *Life and Labor* (O'Reilly, 1911), or the *School and Home Education* magazine (Brown, 1911). In fact, Pratt's toys became very well known (consult also *Bisbee Daily Review*, 1911; *Chicago Daily Tribune*, 1911; *Daily Capital Journal*, 1911; *Geneva Daily Times*, 1911; *New York Times*, 1911; *Sun*, 1911; *Washington Herald*, 1911; *Winona Republican-Herald*, 1911). A photo of the Exhibit's Play Shop (see *Figure 6*) appeared in several publications (e.g., Chicago Child Welfare Exhibit, 1911; Chicago School of Civics and Philanthropy, 1911; O'Reilly, 1911; Zachert, 1913).

1911: Exhibition of Christmas Gifts in Teachers College Educational Museum

Later, in November 1911, Pratt's Do-With™ toys were demonstrated at a fair held by the women of the Unitarian Church in Greenfield, Massachusetts (*Gazette and Courier*, 1911), while from November 24 to December 20, the Teachers College educational museum held an exhibition of Christmas gifts, prepared by Patty Smith Hill. At the time Hill was Assistant Professor of Kindergarten Education at Teachers College. As explained above, both Pratt and Hill became members of the Sub Committee on Home Life in 1910 to organize the toys and playthings exhibition at the 1911 New York Child Welfare Exhibit, and both of them demonstrated Do-With™ toys at the exhibit's Play Shop. Pratt and Hill shared many ideas regarding children's play and concerning toys. It will therefore not come as a surprise that Hill's viewpoints expressed during the opening day of the Christmas Gift Exhibit at the Teachers College educational museum came near Pratt's views. "The purpose of the good toy is to inspire the child to work, to exert its imagination, to occupy itself, in some manner however unconscious, which will bear on its later life," Hill said (*Evening Post*, 1911b). The *Evening Post* reporter stated, "Miss Hill calls her ideal toys 'do with' toys," and added that everything at the exhibition was "designed to make the youngsters work and think to the limit of their pleasure. In a corner resides the 'do-with family,' the members of which could be adjusted to sit down, to walk, or to drive the horse and cart in the stable." Hill had supplemented Do-With™ toys with so-called 'occupation toys,' consisting of little stoves that cooked; laundry articles that could clean the linen of the dolls; and carpet sweepers. The *Evening Post* article further expounded that Hill was "a believer in manual training." "Through manual training...the child learns to sympathize with those who must work — learns to understand."

New York Herald (1911b) had 'Teaching Parents To Buy Toys,' a three-quarter page long illustrated article that cited Pratt's view regarding toys as Christmas gifts.

The ideal toy...should fit into a general scheme of size and use...Miss Caroline Pratt's quaint Dowith toys at the Teachers' College exhibition illustrate the practicability of this idea. She has fashioned the most delightful horses that fit proportionally into stalls, which in turn they were assuredly intended to inhabit, and has made, too, idyllic cows... "To fulfil its full educational obligation," says Miss Pratt, who has done much settlement work and now revels in producing toys that make one wish one were a boy again, "each toy, within its limitations, should work. Each child through play should unconsciously absorb the useful arts."

Note that later *Evening Post* (1911a) had 'Christmas as a Science,' yet another article that discussed the November-December 1911 Teachers College exhibition of Christmas gifts. This article too referred to Pratt's toys. "The wooden playthings called 'Do-With Toys,' specially constructed for little children, are arranged in a scheme which suggests the activities of home and farm" (consult also *New York Daily Tribune*, 1911). Lastly, Merrill (1912, p. 192), while reporting about the exhibit, even spoke of "the now famous 'Do-With Toys'."

Back to 1908: The Birthyear of 'Do-Withs'

Yet, Pratt (1948a, p. 25) later remembered circumstances differently in her autobiography *I Learn From Children*. Her toys most certainly were not that famous that children and their parents bought in large numbers, she hinted:

If the toys could be made commercially successful, I reasoned, their use as an educational medium might follow. And I actually found a manufacturer who was willing to go into the venture.

Mr. Castleman and I worked together long enough to wish that we had never met, for the toys were a total failure.

Pratt had already told that she at some unspecified time in or around 1908 — “full of questions about what kind of toys would best fit children’s own purposes and the spatial limitations of their homes” — visited a friend and saw her / his six-year-old son playing (Pratt, 1948a, p. 23). The visit changed her life. Pratt recounted,

I found the floor covered with a miniature railroad system. He was building with blocks, toys, odd paper boxes, and any material he could find...It was a fascinating thought that came to me...I thought that this was one little boy’s way of learning about the world he lived in; he had observed for himself, had gathered his facts, and was here, before my eyes, writing the perfect child’s textbook of what he had seen...This was thinking, this was learning. This was the way a young child, if freed to do so, would go about educating himself on the subject which was of the most immediate, intense interest to him — the world in which he lived...My thinking raced toward the conclusion that such activity — play activity — might be developed into an ideal means of teaching young children. But I had no opportunity to try it in any of my three jobs. (pp. 23-24).

The whole experience of watching the boy play seemed to come to Pratt as a kind of revelation and made her eventually resign her part-time jobs, for instance, in November 1908, as a carpentry teacher at Hartley House. Pratt wrote, “I had a new plan. Instead of teaching, I would make toys which could be used in the dramatic play of this kind, a play which would reproduce the children’s experience with their own environment” (p. 24).

It remains unclear whether Pratt visited a female friend or a male friend; circumstances suggest she visited a female friend. Yet her story about the visit and the venture of selling her toys confused many readers of her autobiography. Note how mixed up Pratt biographer Beck must have felt after reading the anecdote of the visit in Pratt’s autobiography. Desperately, he utterly distorted Pratt’s story. Beck not only suggested that the revelation had occurred in 1901, when Pratt had decided to resign as a teacher in woodworking at the Philadelphia Normal School for Girls and moved to New York City, but he also inferred that her reference to “a friend” should in fact read “a couple.”

The Philadelphia Normal School was a cul de sac from which the way of escape suggested to Miss Pratt while she was on a visit to a couple who had a six-year-old son. (Beck, 1958, p. 131).

Beck (p. 132) also declared that Pratt’s eventful visit to a friend took place around 1912, logically contradicting his first suggestion that it must have happened in 1901, when Pratt moved from Philadelphia to New York City.

On the other hand, Pratt biographer Carlton (1986, p. 167) rightly stated that the revelation experience must have happened at some time during the first months of 1908. As indicated, it remains unclear whether Pratt visited a female friend or a male friend, or perhaps “a couple” as told by Beck; circumstances, however, suggest she visited a female friend. Note that Pratt biographer Hirsch (1978, p. 30) states — not supported by any sources — that Do-With™ toys “were [later] marketed by the father of the child whom Pratt had observed at play.”

In 1911, Pratt firmly declared in ‘Toys: A Usurped Educational Field,’ published in *The Survey* (1911b) and *The Reform Advocate* (1911c),

Toys covering a variety of industries should be manufactured. The advertising of such toys would revolutionize the attitude towards play in a very few years. The ordinary toy-shops could be used for distribution, and it would probably be possible to make terms with the dealers through which they would bear a part of the advertising. They would permit instructions to be given the saleswomen and, at times, talks on toys in the department by competent persons. To make such toys available to the many, they would have to be manufactured at a minimum rate of interest on the money invested. (Pratt, 1911b, p. 895; 1911c, p. 314).

As already quoted above, Pratt (1948a, p. 25) later wrote in her autobiography, “I actually found a manufacturer who was willing to go into the venture.” She even revealed his name — Castleman — while narrating how their venture failed not long after. If Pratt’s memory was accurate, the failure possibly occurred not long after Gimble Brothers (1910a-b) placed their advertisements in New York City

newspapers announcing that they exclusively sold Pratt's Do-With™ toys. Or, alternatively, perhaps it occurred following the 1911 Christmas Gift exhibit at the Teachers College educational museum. Still, in either case, Pratt's story does not match Hirsch's estimation that manufacturer Castleman was the boy's father; and it does not quite match really enthusiastic press comments in 1910 and 1911 about Pratt's venture — although positive press releases do not mean good sales.

1913: The Birthyear of Play School

Caroline Pratt produced wooden dolls and toys since about late 1908. Selling them, however, was without a doubt not easy. Pratt stated the venture failed completely. In the fall of 1908, she had abandoned her three teaching assignments to design and manufacture toys. In the spring of 1913, then, she returned to teaching for two months, in Hartley House, where six children 'test-played' with her Do-With™ dolls and toys, and also — according to her autobiography — with blocks she had made, later known as Unit Blocks. She observed the children adjusting to their new environment, to the toys, blocks and tools, to each other, to new ideas, to learn to work together. A friend, Edna Smith (see *Note 1* and *Figure 10*), financially backed the experiment (Pratt, 1948a, p. 37). As a consequence, Pratt then, after the summer break, in September 1913, together with Edna Smith set up another pedagogical experiment — they opened Play School in Greenwich Village, New York City.

Often the opening year in the literature is incorrectly mentioned as 1914 (*e.g.* Hauser, 2006; Hirsch, 1978; Semel, 2014; Wolfe, 2002) — after Pratt (1948a, p. 37) herself who introduced the wrong date in her autobiography as “autumn of 1914.” However, several pages after she had told the story of the school's first year (pp. 37- 48) and after she had stated that the “exciting first year [of the school] was not over when [she] began to think of the next” (p. 48), Pratt described a visit to the school by Evelyn Dewey, who “was gathering material for a book of which she was co-author with her father John Dewey, later published under the title *Schools of Tomorrow*” (p. 55). If Pratt would have been right and the school would have been founded in the autumn of 1914, Evelyn Dewey's visit would have happened around July 1915, or later. However, *Schools of Tomorrow* was published in May 1915. Note that Pratt's dating not only contradicts the logical chronology of her life story, it also contradicts the dating indicated in an article published in November 1915 by her life-long companion Helen Marot (1915, p. 16; italics added): Play School “began its *third* year this last September.”

So, in *September 1913*, Pratt rented an apartment at the corner of 4th and 12th Streets, welcoming eleven four- and five-year old children from the locality. Edna Smith again subsidized the experiment, this time for a whole year (Benedict, 1942). In 1914, Marot, Pratt and Smith moved into a small three-story townhouse on Thirteenth Street — the ground floor and part of the second floor reserved for Play School (Pratt, 1948a, p. 48; Rodman, 1915).

Not long after Pratt and Smith founded Play School, Pratt's Do-With™ toys were demonstrated at a toys and playthings exhibition. The November 22, 1913 *Christian Science Monitor* (1913) contains a two-column article about the exhibition — date and place not mentioned. The article discusses several types of toys, including Do-With™ toys, but does not mention Pratt's name, so we cannot be absolutely sure of Pratt's attendance.

The Do-with toys are quaint wooden mortals of many joints, so many that they can be put through almost any motion. They are plainly clad, this farmer and his family, but one recognizes them at once as a family of respectability and sterling worth. They possess a barn which has stalls and a real door to be opened and shut. The farmer can drive into the barn his many-jointed cow and her calf. He can take a bundle of genuine hay from the loft and feed it to the hungry beast. His arms, legs, body, even feet, are capable of being placed in countless positions, and instead of going through his motions by mechanism, it is left to the child to take that form in his own hands and to “dramatize” with his playthings, as the educational phrase goes.

Perhaps then the failure of the venture with Mr. Castleman (Carlton, 1986), described by Pratt in her autobiography (see above), occurred not long after this particular exhibition, most probably after disappointing sales during the 1913 Christmas season?

1914: Pratt Did Not Discard Her Do-With™ Toys

Pratt's autobiography sowed more confusion than merely a puzzlement regarding the exact founding date of her Play School. The readers of *I Learn from Children* may get a distinct impression that Pratt's toy making adventure had ended *before* she founded Play School.

Pratt (1948a) wrote,

The fact that *my first and only business venture* lived and died without making the faintest mark on the world did not grieve me unduly. (p. 25; italics added)

This, however, has not been a reality. Contrary to the thought that readers probably formed after reading Pratt's narrative (namely: she had completely abandoned her Do-With™ toys adventure), Pratt had only temporarily given up on selling her toys and dolls.

In February 1914, Patty Smith Hill gave a talk before the New York Public School Kindergarten Association, auspiciously showing Pratt's Do-With™ dolls to her public. The April 1914 *Kindergarten Review* (1914) reported Hill's talk.

[Hill] first presented various definitions of toys and their classification: the three toys of universal significance being the ball, blocks, and doll...Through doll plays children reverse attitude, and, instead of receiving care, they give it. At the close of the talk Miss Hill showed a number of dolls of different construction — one set, the Caroline Pratt Do-With-Dolls, — also the Schoenhut dolls, made of wood with ball-bearing joints — and she suggested the need of a scheme of dolls, — a family in the right proportion.

Next, nonetheless, at some time in the 1914 spring — perhaps encouraged by Hill's February 1914 talk — Pratt made another attempt to market her Do-With™ toys.

First, the New York City Stryvelyne Shop (1914a-b) advertised in the May 5 and May 23, 1914, Boston newspaper *Christian Science Monitor*, "In cooperation with Miss Caroline Pratt, who announces many new toys and toy schemes, we now make and sell the DO WITH TOYS." Pratt (1914a) placed an almost similar ad in the June 1914 issue of *Country Life in America*, "Do-With Toys are now made and sold by The Stryvelyne Shop coöperating with Miss Caroline Pratt who announces many new toys and toy schemes" (see *Figure 8*). Interestingly, in this respect, is the fact that around the same time, mid-1914, the National Congress of Mothers and Parent-Teacher Associations in Washington, D.C. published 'The Real Joy in Toys,' Pratt's (1914b) contribution of a chapter on toys to the 1914 *Parents and Their Problems* book series. On December 5, 1914 the Stryvelyn Shop advertised in the *Evening Post*, "Our toys are originated and made by us in the City of New York."

A further, second, indication that Pratt was again busy having her Do-With™ toys and dolls manufactured and sold are two other 1914 publications: a story in the December 5 *Christian Science Monitor* (Pratt, 1914b) that almost in its entirety quotes 'The Toys That Children Like,' an article published earlier by Pratt (1914c) in the December issue of *The Woman's Magazine*. These two articles explain why children should not play with so-called 'unrelated toys.' "It is too much to expect children to play with unrelated toys. It is as inconsistent as to expect a gardener to garden with a pitchfork, a shovel and a hammer," Pratt stated (*Christian Science Monitor*, 1914a). Instead children ought to play with 'related toys' that "indicate the play that may be carried out with them." Both articles also refer to a boy named "Fritz" who played with Do-With™ toys *as well as* with blocks. In fact, "Fritz had blocks especially made for him, as there were no suitable ones on the market." These blocks most probably concern those devised by Pratt herself — later known as Unit Blocks.

Although Fritz was not familiar with what goes on in a country barn, the possession of a horse and cart, a cow and a pig immediately threw him into a play scheme the details of which occupied him for months. The addition of a calf, and later a colt, renewed the old play and added new features. At the vanishing point of the play a man doll was introduced, and again the process began all over. Early in the play it became necessary to have a place to shelter the animals, and later the man had to have a house to live in. For this purpose Fritz had blocks especially made for him, as there were no suitable ones on the market. The block-building the boy did for a purpose was a marvel. (*Christian Science Monitor*, 1914a; Pratt, 1914c).

Pratt declared that “in order to have a play ‘succeed’ it is necessary to treat it quite as seriously as work, and in many respects to apply the self-same principles.” She had never bought a toy without having put several questions to it. One of the questions is, “What can my child do with you?” According to her there are “Look-on toys” children just cannot really play with, for instance because their mechanical devices do not allow for (much) play activity. On the other hand, there are ‘related’ “Do-withs” — toys unspecified enough which allow for diverse, ‘related,’ play activities. Another question is, “Are you the right size?” Toys as “tools of play” should match in size with other toys, was Pratt’s opinion; the toys’ sizes must be proportionate when played with. The third question is, “Are you pleasing to look at?”

DO-WITH TOYS are now made and sold by
The Stryvelyne Shop coöperating with Miss Caro-
line Pratt who announces many new toys and toy
schemes.

Figure 8: Advertisement in the June 1914 *Country Life in America* (Pratt, 1914a).

Pratt’s final observation:

Those first few years when children play with toys are the years when fundamental habits are formed. Such habits as “thinking things out” and “keeping at” things are most easily formed in childhood and may be more readily fostered through play than later on through work. (*Christian Science Monitor*, 1914a; Pratt, 1914c).

Taken together: advertisements placed by Pratt and by the Stryvelyne Shop in 1914, Pratt’s book chapter, and her article in *The Woman’s Magazine* (in shorted form also in *Christian Science Monitor*), seem to constitute parts of a program to sell Do-With™ dolls and toys. However, this second attempt of Pratt’s business enterprise trying to put the dolls and toys on the market never really ‘came on steam.’ Research of mid-1914 and early-1915 New York City newspapers shows that the Stryvelyne Shop, Inc. — “manufacturers of educational toys for the up-to-date play-room” (*New York Tribune*, 1914) — was incorporated in April 1914 (*Bookseller, Newsdealer and Stationer*, 1914). Four months later, in August 1914, Stryvelyne Shop leased the twelfth loft in a new building at 7 to 11 West 45th Street, New York City (*New York Tribune*, 1914). Yet, in spite of all this, Stryvelyne Shop already went bankrupt in January 1915 (*New York Press*, 1915; *New York Times*, 1915; *Sun*, 1915), thereby destroying the second attempt of Pratt’s business enterprise trying to sell her toys and dolls. Pratt had to give up her venture of selling Do-With™ toys and dolls — for the second time.

Then again, evidence exists in the archives of the Bureau of Educational Experiments that even as late as during the summer of 1916, Caroline Pratt had not yet given up her wish of manufacturing and selling dolls and toys. Pratt was one of the Bureau’s charter members since May 1916. Bureau members met almost daily in various committees and councils to discuss the progress of work. Minutes of the June 2, 1916, Working Council meeting state that a “vote was taken that the Chair appoint a committee who shall consider a plan for the manufacture of the ‘Do-with Toys’ and that the same committee shall consider the general question of educational toys” (Minutes Working Council, June 2nd, 1916; Bureau of Educational Experiments Archives, Bank Street College of Education, New York City). However, nothing came of the plans (Staring, 2013a-b, 2015; Staring & Aldridge, 1915b).

1915, Play School: Reports in *New York Tribune*

The Stryvelyne Shop’s insolvency problems most probably constituted great personal problems in Pratt’s life too, but there are no sources confirming this ‘educated guess.’

Still, 1915 turned out to become a very successful year for Caroline Pratt and her Play School. Pratt’s publications of the time — about her educational philosophy and her specific approach to education, about the play, and about (her) dolls, toys and blocks — had made an impression in educational circles (consult Pratt, 1911bc, 1912a-b, 1913, 1914b-c; Staring, 1213a-b, 2015). In the winter of 1915, Play School started to receive interested visitors. Teacher and journalist Henrietta Rodman (consult Carter, 2016) visited the school first. She reported her experiences in the *New York Tribune*. Rodman (1915) opened by asking,

Have you ever gone to the Play School, at 206 West Thirteenth Street? It's as full of toys as Santa Claus's pack, and as full of children as the old woman's shoe, when she didn't know what to do. But Miss Caroline Pratt knows exactly what to do. She gives the toys to the children, and then watches them play. Once in a while she makes a suggestion; but the children work out their own ideas nearly all of the time. The marvel of Miss Pratt's toys is that they're not just cunning and pretty, and what they are, like most toys. They can all be taken apart and put together again in any number of fascinating ways.

Rodman declared she was happy to have found a place where children “get knowledge of life and opportunity for creative activity,” which according to her are “the things” children were “not getting in the public schools.” What is especially fascinating to detect is the fact that through Rodman's description of toys used in Play School we learn that Pratt had not at all discarded her Do-With™ dolls and toys after the two failures to market them — through Gimbel Brothers, New York City, 1910-11, and through the Stryvelyne Shop, New York City, 1914-15. Rodman's report describes what she saw in the various schoolrooms. Interesting is the fact that she noticed the use of large quantities of blocks in Play School. “I entered a room, and there I saw a wooden river flowing between banks of blocks.” Rodman cited Pratt, “You see, one boy built the church and another this house; then they linked the two by this block road.” Rodman also depicted a “domestic scene in the next room...peopled with *delightfully jointed dolls*, which sat on chairs that fitted them” (Italics added). It turned out that the chairs had been built by a boy of six who had come up with his own thinking as well as his own answers with regard to chair sizes.

A few days later, journalist Doris Fleischman (1915) published ‘A Play School That Is Frankly Experimental,’ a near page-long illustrated an interview with Pratt, also in the *New York Tribune*. The article's illustrations with captions show two five-years-old boys at a work-bench (caption: “Manual Artists”); two two-years-old children, a girl and a boy, playing on the floor, each as if it was in her / his own ‘cubicle’ (caption: “Separate compartments insure freedom from outside distraction to the pupil engrossed in an individual problem”); the four children playing on and under a balcony (caption: “The balcony gives more floor space to all”). Other photos show of one of the five-years-old boys painting a self-made car (caption: “Even he has an automobile, but it must be painted up”) and a girl working at a carpenter's bench (caption: “Her sex does not debar her from manual training here”). Several illustrations would later appear in another newspaper article (Moses, 1919) and in Bulletins issued by the NYC Bureau of Educational Experiments. (Note that the main assembly room in Hartley House, where Pratt had experimented with a group of six children in the spring of 1913, has a large balcony. Did this Hartley House main assembly room balcony perhaps inspire Pratt to build a balcony in her school?)

Fleischman without any hesitation proclaimed the Play School — “under the direction of Miss Caroline Pratt and Miss Edna Smith” — the “School of the Future.” Her article explains that the school's children played games they want, wherever they wanted to play them — and learned while playing them. The children were not compelled to learn, but they were not forced to play either. Fleischman described children running about and playing on a balcony, at the sand box, at a workbench, or making a clock, or playing with wooden cars, or drawing spontaneously. The drawing was a mode of expression and it served alternative purposes since it helped children observe their world; it helped them express themselves; it helped them express thoughts about observations; and it aided fine motor co-ordination of their fingers. “Our school,” Pratt explained to Fleischman, “is an experiment in education.”

When the children go on any of their numerous expeditions in search of knowledge they return with one impression uppermost. It may not be the one which the teacher had in mind, but the child is a separate personality, and the fact that he has observed and thought about any one thing and found it interesting shows that the trip was a valuable one. For instance, when they go across the river to see a huge factory, perhaps the next day, when each one goes to the drawing board, the pictures which they draw will vary greatly. One may draw the factory. But another is more than likely to draw the great Brooklyn Bridge, which it has seen for the first time, and the vast expanse of water below. Another may try to picture the sunshine.

Pratt clarified that lower-grades' teaching in public schools was determinedly based on prematurely acquiring skills of reading and writing. The same was true for Montessori, she pronounced. Play School children, on the other hand, would learn how to read and write when they were a little older.

1915, Play School: Reports in *Schools of To-Morrow* and in *the New Republic*

As indicated above, at some time in late-1914, or perhaps early in 1915, Evelyn Dewey visited Play School, conducting research for a book she co-authored with her father, John Dewey. In *Schools of To-Morrow*, published in May 1915, Evelyn and John Dewey (1915a-b) reported that Pratt's school "organizes all the work around the play activities of little children" (p. 116); that every child in the school "has floor space of his own with a rug, and screens to isolate him sufficiently so that his work is really individual" (p. 117); and that Pratt's role as a teacher was "to teach the pupil processes and control of tools, not in a prearranged scale but as they are needed in construction" (p. 118). The Deweys cited Pratt:

"The experiment concerns itself with getting subject-matter first hand, and it is assumed that the child has much information to begin with, that he is adding to it day by day, that it is possible to direct his attention so that he may get his information in a more related way; and with applying such information to individual *schemes of play with related toys and blocks* as well as expressing himself through such general means as drawing, dramatization, and spoken language." (p. 117; italics added).

Evelyn and John Dewey found the toys present in the school on the whole very good. They even described them, that is to say, they sketched dolls and construction blocks.

There are flat wooden dolls about half an inch thick, men, women, and children, whose joints bend so that they will stay in any position; all sorts of farm animals and two or three kinds of little wagons that fit the dolls; quantities of *big blocks that fasten together with wooden pegs*, so that the houses and bridges do not fall down. Everything is strongly made on the simplest plan, so that material can be used not only freely but also effectively. (pp. 118-119).

Helen Marot (1915) listed the school's toys, dolls and blocks in *The New Republic*:

Toys are a serious part of the equipment. They have been selected with careful regard for the use to which the children will put them. The men, women and child dolls are proportionate in size, and related to them are horses, carts, domestic animals, trains of cars, and *all sizes of blocks* for use as building material. The children supplement these toys with boats, auto-trucks, derricks, steam shovels and house furnishings which they make at the bench. (p. 16; italics added).

All the above 1915 descriptions and photos of toys in Play School by the Deweys, by Fleischman, by Marot, and by Rodman, sketch Pratt's 'Do-withs.' One of two photos facing page 118 in *Schools of To-Morrow* depicts a boy — who by the way was also depicted in photos in Fleischman's article — playing with the Do-With™ horse and cart and with a Do-With™ cow. A photo in Fleischman's (1915) *New York Tribune* article depicts toddlers playing on the floor, each as it were in her / his own 'cubicle;' a girl plays with blocks and a Do-With™ horse and cart. Four years later, the photo was published again in the *New York Tribune* (Moses, 1919) as well as in Bulletins issued by the NYC Bureau of Educational Experiments (Bureau of Educational Experiments, 1917, p. 8; n.d., p. 7; Hunt (Ed.), 1918, p. 32. See *Figure 9*). The photos deliver unconditional proof that Play School children in 1915 played with Pratt's Do-With™ toys and dolls *along with* with various kinds of blocks. In contrast, the vague 1915 descriptions of blocks used in Pratt's Play School in the abovementioned four 1915 reports make it very difficult to estimate whether indeed the blocks described were Unit Blocks Pratt had devised.

Figure 9: Toddlers are playing on the floor (Bureau of Educational Experiments, n.d., p. 7).

It seems very likely that Evelyn Dewey during her visit to Play School did not really notice the variety of blocks in the rooms. Her description of blocks that can be attached to each other by wooden pins may indicate they were Peg-Lock Blocks, at the time manufactured by the Peg-Lock Block Company of New York. Fleischman’s article does not present a description of blocks at all. On the other hand, Marot’s description of blocks used in Pratt’s school appears to depict familiar Unit Blocks sizes.

But then again, expert analysis of the abovementioned photo in Fleischman’s 1915 article depicting two toddlers playing on the floor shows a girl playing with basic Unit Blocks (see *Figure 9*), while there are also basic Unit Blocks behind the boy, as well as several so-called ‘middlies’ in front of him — blocks twice the size of basic Unit Blocks (Cuffaro, 2010). This specific photograph warrants the authoritative conclusion by Harriet K. Cuffaro that in 1915 Play School children played with Unit Blocks designed by Pratt.

Was Pratt really inspired by the blocks of Patty Smith Hill?

In 1991, Harriet K. Cuffaro, my mentor in the field of early childhood education, paid attention to the use of blocks and other materials as “tools with which the children give form to and express their understanding of the world and the meanings they have constructed” (p. 64). Cuffaro first discussed the use of Froebelian blocks, and next how between 1887 and 1894 Anna Bryan was testing alternative blocks in the kindergartens she directed in Louisville, Kentucky. Bryan allowed children to experiment and “to play imaginatively” with the Froebelian ‘gifts’ (p. 68). Bryan’s pioneering experimental work inspired, amongst others, her colleague Patty Smith Hill as well as the Dewey Laboratory School in Chicago. Cuffaro also discussed blocks designed by Patty Smith Hill and by Caroline Pratt. Interesting in this respect is that she did not see a direct connection between Hill’s blocks and Pratt’s blocks. Other educators who write about the origin of Pratt’s Unit Blocks often tell a story not really dissimilar from the following anecdote, told by a former City and Country School teacher only a few years ago: “Inspired by the hollow blocks invented by Patty Hill at Teachers College in New York City, Pratt designed unit blocks for use in The Play School” (Smith, 2015, p. xi). Repeatedly the story is told that Pratt either designed her blocks in 1913 (*e.g.*, Winters, 2002) or in 1914 — depending on whether the storyteller accepts Play School was founded in 1913 or in 1914. In fact, many educators even think Pratt designed her wooden jointed dolls and wooden toys as well as her blocks when she opened her school. Well, Pratt began designing her dolls and toys in 1908, that must be clear now, given the paragraphs above in this case study. But, did Pratt design her blocks in 1913 or 1914, in reality? No!

Part of the problem of chronology and possible influence on Pratt that is being unfolded here is the fact that such anecdotes seem to be so ineradicable; nobody seems to have researched the matter thoroughly. Part of the problem is that other Pratt biographers were not aware of Pratt and Hill’s partnerships in organizing exhibitions in 1910 and 1911. And, frankly, part of the problem lies in the collapsed chronology in Pratt’s autobiography.

General History of Patty Smith Hill’s Floor Blocks

But first: What is the chronology in case of Patty Smith Hill’s ‘hollow blocks,’ that is, her Floor Blocks? Cuffaro sketched their origin:

The first Hill floor blocks in all probability were derived from the original enlargement of the [Froebel] gifts by Bryan in Louisville. The set consisted of seven shapes based on a six-inch unit with the longest block, an oblong, measuring 24 inches in length. During the period when Hill directed the Kindergarten Department at Teachers College, this set was altered in design and dimension. Grooved corner blocks were added in heights of 15 inches to 27 inches into which blocks varying in length from 6 inches to 36 inches would fit. The large structures constructed with these blocks were stabilized by using pegs, copper wire rods, and girders and became houses, post offices, stores, and restaurants into which children entered and in which they dramatized directly their understanding of families and occupations. The size of blocks communicates to children the scale in which they are to work. (Cuffaro, 1991, pp. 71-72; compare Cuffaro, 2012).

Around 1894, Hill succeeded Anna Bryan as Superintendent of the Louisville Free Kindergarten Association and as Director of the Training School for Kindergarten and Primary Teachers in Louisville, Kentucky (Lascares & Hinitz, 2011; Snyder, 1972). In 1900, Hill explained in *Kindergarten Magazine*,

[...] at Dr. Gulick’s suggestion we are introducing heavy blocks (6x3x1½ inches) to be used in absolutely free play in groups either at the table or on the floor. Thus we feel the children are gaining skill in handling both large and small blocks and adjusting themselves to working under conditions both of guidance and freedom. (Hill, 1900, p. 408).

Much later, Hill would expand on the subject — during an interview, in *Survey Graphic*.

In 1898 I studied with Dr. Luther Gulick who had the first school of play in America, and I took for my problem a new set of building blocks on a scale sufficiently large to enable children to play in the houses, stores, and barns they built. We worked on this scheme twelve or thirteen years before we devised our present set of blocks which schools all over the world are using. (Amidon, 1927, p. 509).

And a decade later, Hill addressed the origin of her blocks again — this time in a 1936 letter:

In 1895 when these experiments were initiated under my supervision in the kindergartens of Louisville, Ky., I had just returned from a summer’s study under G. Stanley Hall and his colleagues where psychologists, physicians and hygienists criticized severely the traditional kindergartens of the day, for their use of small blocks and handwork which threw strain upon the young child’s small undeveloped muscles of eye and hand.

In 1898 there was [a] conference of psychologists and physicians under the direction of Luther Halsey Gulick, where my first experiments along these lines were exhibited and reported. The encouragement is given then and in later studies under Dr. John Dewey, made me more and more determined to devise building blocks and other materials sufficiently large to demand the use of the large fundamental muscles of little children. (Letter by Hill, cited in Carlton, 1986, p. 181).

Combining the above information (compare also Hall, 1898, Sherwood & Freshwater, 2013), we can deduce that Hill at long last produced the end-result of her building blocks experiments in 1911. Three years later, Hill edited ‘Experimental Studies in Kindergarten Theory and Practice,’ a special issue of *Teachers College Record*. She introduced the building blocks she had devised — now known as ‘Hill Floor Blocks.’

We have introduced some blocks, which are much larger than those of Froebel or Montessori, for use on the floor and in group work. These are related as far as being based upon a unit of measurement is considered. They provide boards — a long-felt need in constructive materials of the kindergarten, with which the children can construct bridges, floors, and houses sufficiently large for the children to get in and play “Lady-come-to-see” or store, to their heart’s content. (Hill, 1914, p. 8).

Instructor at Teachers College and its Horace Mann Kindergarten Meredith Smith (1914) added, “With the large floor blocks used in the Horace Mann kindergarten the bridge may be built large enough and strong enough for the children to walk over drawing their wagons or carrying their dolls” (p. 21). And, “With Professor Hill’s floor blocks children may build their stores large enough for one to stand behind the counter and others to come in and buy” (p. 23).

Lastly, in 1921, in *The Home Kindergarten Manual*, Hill stated,

We have introduced some blocks, which are much larger than those of Froebel or Montessori, for use on the floor and in group work. These are related as far as being based upon a unit of measurement is considered. They provide boards — a long-felt need in the constructive materials of the kindergarten — with which the children can construct bridges, floors, and houses sufficiently large for the children to get in, play “Lady-come-to-see” or store, to their heart’s content. (Hill, 1921, p. 426).

The 1918 edition of *A Catalogue of Play Equipment* — the eighth Bulletin published by the NYC Bureau of Educational Experiments — describes Hill’s end product.

“*Hill Floor Blocks*,” manufactured and sold by A. Schoenhut & Co., of Philadelphia. They are of hard maple and come in seven sizes, from 3” squares to oblongs of 24”, the unit block being 6” in length...They are the invention of Professor Patty Smith Hill of Teachers College, Columbia University, and are used in The Teachers College Kindergarten and in many other schools. (Hunt (Ed.), 1918, p. 33).

A photo of an advertisement in Wolf (2002) shows that fourteen years later, in 1932, the Appleton Wood Products Company of Appleton, Wisconsin sold Hill Floor Blocks.

Photos in the abovementioned Bureau of Educational Experiments Bulletin show children playing with Hill Floor Blocks at Gregory Avenue School in West Orange. Earlier, Smith’s aforementioned 1914 article, and later, Hill’s 1923 book *A Conduct Curriculum for the Kindergarten and the First Grade* also contain photos of ‘large floor blocks’ or ‘Hill Blocks,’ that is, Hill Floor Blocks (Hill, 1923, photo facing p. 24; Smith, 1914, photos facing p. 22). A photo in Evelyn and John Dewey’s 1915 book *Schools of Tomorrow* belongs to the earliest showing Hill’s floor blocks (Dewey & Dewey, 1915a-b; photo facing p. 8).

Agnes Burke (1919) referenced the socializing aspect of ‘Patty Hill blocks,’ that is, Hill Floor Blocks, in *Teachers College Record*:

This is a set of building blocks by Professor Hill, of Teachers College, and now on sale at A. Schoenhut Co., Philadelphia. The set is made up of blocks in various lengths and sufficient in size and number to make possible the construction of such houses as can be entered and used by children. The blocks have proved one of the most popular materials, especially with the boys. They stimulate social organization as well as construction. (p. 119).

Lastly, the *Evening Post* (1911b) cited Hill’s captivating conviction that “a good box of building blocks is worth all the electric toys in the world.”

General History of Caroline Pratt’s Unit Blocks

Cuffaro also wrote about Pratt blocks, yet did not indicate a connection to Hill’s Floor Blocks.

[Pratt’s] unit blocks have remained as the standard blocks used in early childhood settings. In contrast to the Hill blocks, the stability of a structure built with the Pratt blocks is achieved through the skill and architectural understanding of the builder rather than through the placement of pegs and girdens. This fact, in combination with the smaller dimensions of the Pratt blocks, communicated to children that the buildings they created would not accommodate their direct participation for prolonged periods of play. While similar themes of home, stores, and occupations also emerged in play with the unit blocks, their smaller size elicited a different type of dramatic play, a form that was intentionally encouraged and supported by Pratt. She created scaled wooden people and animals with which children populated their buildings. With these symbolic representations of self the children revealed their thoughts and feelings in play, telling and acting stories about themselves and the world in which they lived.

In creating these figures, Caroline Pratt offered children a supplementary material to the blocks that increased their freedom to create their own texts and interactions. (Cuffaro, 1991, pp. 72-73; see also Cuffaro, 2012).

According to Pratt biographer Carlton (1986) it was in 1910 that Pratt visited Hill at the Horace Mann School after Hill’s promotion from Instructor to Assistant Professor of Kindergarten Education and her appointment as Head of the Department of Kindergarten Education at Teachers College. The promotion and appointment took effect on July 1, 1910. Pratt observed how the children played with large blocks; Hill was still experimenting with their design. Later, Pratt would recount the event in her autobiography.

And I had seen children playing with blocks at Teachers College, when the gifted Patty Hill had charge of the kindergarten there.

She had designed the blocks herself, for the children in her classes to use during their free periods. They were not a part of her teaching program, but I had watched what the children had done with them during those short play periods when they could do what they liked. To me those play periods seemed the most important part of the school day.

Of all the materials which I had seen offered to children (“thrust upon” would better fit the situation), these blocks of Patty Hill’s seemed to me best suited to children’s purposes. A simple geometrical shape could become any number of things to a child. It could be a truck or a boat or the car of a train. He could build buildings with it from barns to skyscrapers. I could see the children of my as yet unborn school constructing a complete community with blocks. (Pratt, 1948a, p. 29).

Note that Pratt said about Hill’s blocks that she saw how they could invite children to all kinds of play schemes. Pratt did *not* claim that Hill’s experimental blocks formed a defining inspiration for her own blocks. Since Pratt — immediately following the story of her visit to Hill’s kindergarten — told the history of her experiments in Hartley House and the co-founding of Play School with Edna Smith (see above), the readers of her autobiography were not only inclined to assume that the visit had happened immediately prior to the opening of the school, but also that this visit was the decisive moment for Pratt to design her own blocks.

Could it be that Pratt and Hill already knew each other before 1910? Pratt biographer Carlton (1986) states that Pratt “became acquainted with Patty Smith Hill’s brother Archibald Alexander Hill and his family” (p. 178) at the Hartley House settlement, where she worked from 1901 to November 1908. However, there is no confirmation of Carlton’s claim in the literature. But if true, Pratt may have heard (much) about Patty Smith Hill before she met her. Hill worked and lived in New York City since 1906. A first meeting may have occurred at some time between 1906 and mid-1910, but also independent of Hill’s brother’s intervention, for instance during the 1909 AGM of the International Kindergarten Union, held in Buffalo, New York, where Pratt showed her toys for the first time to the public and where Hill retired as President of the International Kindergarten Union (*Kindergarten Review*, 1909b).

As clarified above, Pratt and Hill met regularly in late-1910 and early in 1911. Other Pratt biographers did not mention that Pratt and Hill knew each other well at the time. Neither Beck (1958), Carlton (1986), Hauser (2002, 2006), nor Hirsch (1978), or others, have described that Pratt and Hill were on a committee, established in 1910, to organize the toys and playthings exhibition at the Child Welfare Exhibits in New York and in Chicago in 1911. They did not mention that *both* Hill and Pratt demonstrated Pratt’s Do-With™ dolls and toys at the New York Child Welfare Exhibit. As well, other Pratt biographers did not mention either that Pratt had been invited to have her Do-With™ dolls and toys demonstrated at the November-December 1911 exhibition of Christmas gifts, held at the Teachers College educational museum, well thought-out and put together by Hill.

So, in late-1910 and in 1911, Hill and Pratt already knew each other well, worked together, sharing interests and educational views. Hill knew of Pratt’s Do-With™ dolls, toys *and* blocks, and Pratt knew of Hill’s experiments with large floor blocks. How much they influenced each other’s block designing program remains unclear in the literature.

The 1918 *A Catalogue of Play Equipment* states that building blocks used by Caroline Pratt at her Play School,

[...] are of white wood, the unit block being $1\frac{3}{8}$ ” x $2\frac{3}{4}$ ” x $5\frac{1}{2}$ ” [meaning they are $5\frac{1}{2}$ inches long by $2\frac{3}{4}$ inches wide by $1\frac{3}{8}$ inches in height; J.S.]. They range in size from half units...to blocks four times the unit in length (22”)” (Hunt (Ed.), 1918, p. 32).

Sally Cartwright (1988, p. 44) later simply explained,

Their sizes are fractions and multiples of a carefully designed unit block. And, particularly important to young children, each change of size is made only in one dimension.

As indicated by Cuffaro above, differences in size and shape between Hill and Pratt’s blocks are easily detectable. Photographs in *A Catalogue of Play Equipment* show children who play with blocks designed by Pratt. The third edition of the Bureau of Educational Experiments Bulletin states that Pratt’s

blocks, used in the City and Country School (the former Play School) and in a few other experimental schools like the Bureau of Educational Experiments Nursery School in New York City and Home School in Sparkill, New York could be obtained on order from Pendleton and Townsend, Patterson, New York (Hunt (Ed.), 1924). Six years later, Stanton (1930) described a set of building blocks very familiar to the Pratt Unit Blocks and stated that these blocks were on sale at Industrial Arts Co-operative Service, New York City as well as at Pendleton and Townsend in Patterson. Wolf (2002) later explained that the Educational Equipment Company manufactured Unit Blocks. She added,

Pratt never patented these blocks, even when City and Country School was in dire financial difficulties. She never gained any monetary compensation for these very successful blocks. It is interesting that their future manufacture by a variety of companies retained the proportions and sizes of the original Pratt blocks. (p. 327).

Interestingly, later publications show that children gave (nick-)names to various Unit Blocks.

There were “brickies” ($1\frac{3}{8}$ ” x $2\frac{3}{4}$ ” x $5\frac{1}{2}$ ”), “middlies” (double the size of “brickies”) and “longies” (double the size of “middlies” and four times the size of “brickies”). There were “butteries” (the size of a stick of butter and half the size of a “brickie”) and “squaries” (half the size of a “brickie”) and “triangles,” half the size of “squaries.” There were “rampies” (again half of a “brickie”), and “roundies” (cylinders). (Smith, 2015, p. 31).

Even though the word ‘block’ rarely appears in the first brochure of Pratt’s City and Country School in 1919, almost inattentive and despite pictures of children playing with Unit Blocks (City and Country School, 1919), blocks designed by Pratt were prominently mentioned in 1919 and later publications about the school (e.g., Severance 1919). During the mid-1920s, Caroline Pratt, a charter member of the Bureau of Educational Experiments since 1916 and Principal of City and Country School that in 1919 became the Bureau’s laboratory kindergarten and primary school, and Jessie Stanton, one of the school’s early teachers (see Note 3), described both the practice and theory of block play and block building at City and Country School (e.g., Pratt (Ed.), 1924; Pratt & Stanton, 1926; Stanton, 1930).

There was a steady increase in the importance of the use of blocks in City and Country School during the 1920s. This is clearly reflected in the weight that Pratt has placed on the blocks and to block building at her school during these years. For example, the index in *Experimental Practice in the City and Country School* states that three pages are dedicated to blocks plus four pages to block building (Pratt (Ed.), 1924, p. 295). The index in Pratt and Stanton’s *Before Books* — issued only two years later — refers to four pages “experience with blocks,” plus forty-six pages devoted to blocking building (Pratt & Stanton, 1926, p. 341). Over the years, Pratt, the blocks she had designed, and her theories related to block play became well known in the United States (Wolf, 2002), Iceland (Einarsdóttir, 2015), mainland Europe (Philippi-Siewertsz van Reesema, 1949), and even in New Zealand (Manning, 2018). Unit Blocks, Pratt’s building blocks, became known under very different names. For instance, Agnes Benedict (1942) called them Caroline Pratt Blocks in 1942, while a year later she and Adele Franklin indicated that the blocks were known as the Pratt Project Play Blocks (Franklin & Benedict, 1943).

Harriet M. Johnson — co-founder of the Bureau of Educational Experiments in 1916 and Principal of its Nursery School since 1919 (Johnson, 1928; Staring & Aldridge, 2015a) — stated that Pratt “has never given [the blocks she designed] her name and so they are found on the market under the name of the manufacturer and under various trade names” (Johnson, 1933, p. 6). Interestingly, in this respect, is that on December 14, 1936 Pratt started a brief correspondence with Hill about the giving a name to, and the patenting of, blocks they had designed in the past. “It seems that the blocks with the unit, brick size, which we have used and developed,” Pratt (1936) wrote, “are being sold by numerous manufacturers who are taking liberties with them.” She added, “The man who is making them for our trade wishes the protection of my name, which I have refused up to date because, while I have developed the use of them, I did not originate them.” Pratt asked Hill, “I don’t know whether you originated them or not. As there are already Patty Hill blocks, what shall we do about these? I shall be glad to have my name used, if there isn’t anyone who has a better right.” Hill (1937) replied, “We were so green, when we were working out our blocks experimentally with the children before large audiences, that we did not know that to have had ‘patent applied for’ stamped on them would have given us future protection.” Hill mentioned that someone had applied for a patent of her blocks not long before she tried to patent them herself. And about blocks

developed by Pratt she noted, “Your blocks...seem utterly unlike ours. So I imagine you can go straight ahead with yours, & I wish you all success.” Pratt (1937) then replied that she would give her name “to a manufacturer to use in connection” with her blocks. “This does not mean that I shall get anything from them. It will merely help to protect him from other manufacturers,” she explained.

History of Pratt’s Unit Blocks, further examined

We have seen above that the children in Pratt’s Play School definitely played with Pratt’s Unit Blocks in 1915. The question then arises: When were the blocks first created and introduced? November 22, 1913, *Christian Science Monitor* (1913), addressed a “busy child” playing with Do-With™ toys *as well as* with blocks in an article titled ‘Many Toys Shown In An Up-To-Date Exhibition’. However, although the text bespeaks Do-With™ toys in direct relation to blocks, Pratt’s name is not mentioned.

The Do-with toys are quaint wooden mortals of many joints, so many that they can be put through almost any motion...For he must be a busy child is he is to play with these toys. No chance for him to idle — every one calls forth his activities. Instead of an aeroplane that flies of itself, *there are building blocks that can be combined* to form a cathedral or a cottage, as his taste may dictate. Observe that “dictate.” Free-will is a big factor in the toys the child should have. (Italics added).

Are there any other indications that Pratt may have discussed (prototypes of) Unit Blocks, that is, the blocks she had devised, before 1915? Pratt sketched the origin of the blocks in the December 1914 *Woman’s Magazine* whilst spelling out the play of boy “Fritz.”

Just before the Great Birthday, little Fritz has a birthday of his own...Early in [Fritz’s] play it became necessary to have a place to shelter the [toy] animals, and later the man [= Do-With doll] had to have a house to live in. *For this purpose Fritz had blocks especially made for him, as there were and still are no suitable ones on the market.* The block-building the boy did *for a purpose* was a marvel. I know what my friends mean when they say their children will not play with blocks. But I never had had this experience with my own, because from the start they have had a reason for building. (First italics added).

Note that boy Fritz also figures in ‘The Real Joy in Toys,’ Pratt’s contribution of a chapter to the *Parents and Their Problems* book series published earlier that year.

With such a collection of do-with toys, Fritz, aged four, milked his cow, turned the milk into a can, harnessed his horse, dressed the man that had been put to bed the night before, put the can of milk on the wagon, and the man drove over to the dolls’ house to deliver the breakfast milk. Does your child carry out such a scheme as this? (Pratt, 1914b, p. 121).

In 1911, Pratt (1911b, p. 894; 1911c, p. 313) also wrote about a boy called Fritz:

Take, for example, the case of little Fritz. At the age of four he had some of the Do-with toys which are worked out in a farm scheme. He milked his cow, turned the milk into a can, harnessed his horse, dressed the man who had been put to bed the night before, put the can of milk on the wagon, and the man drove over to the dolls’ house with the milk for breakfast. Does your child carry out a plan such as this? (Here a voice says ‘No, but Fritz had had farm experience.’) No, Fritz had had no farm experience. He had obtained his play ‘content’ largely from the toys. This is easily proved by the fact that he milked his cow by pumping up and down the ‘handle’ as he called it. He had to be taken to see a cow milked to change his practice. (Pratt, 1911b, p. 894; 1911c, p. 313).

And, Pratt indicated that children who visited the January 1911 Child Welfare exhibit

[...] wandered into the shop from the aisles and settled down comfortably with the blocks and wooden animals and dolls. (Pratt, 1911b, p. 894; 1911c, p. 314).

Lastly, Mary O’Reilly’s (1911) report about Pratt’s Child Welfare Exhibit’s Play Shop in *Life and Labor* explicitly refers to Do-Withs and “a stock of *neatly fitting blocks* with which relays of children played all day long” (p. 197; italics added).

Comparing Pratt’s two 1914 texts with her earlier 1911 text, we may, on the one hand, safely conclude that the 1911 Fritz *is* the 1914 Fritz. On the other hand, Pratt’s 1911 article (that appeared in two

magazines) reports her observations and experience at the Child Welfare Exhibit held in January of that year. This means that she must have already devised and made prototypes of her Unit Blocks as early as *before* the start of the Child Welfare Exhibit, that is, in 1910. The fact that Pratt in her report talked about “the blocks, wooden animals and dolls” as forming one whole (created by her) gives strength to the conclusion. O’Reilly’s (1911) report about the Child Welfare Exhibit’s Play Shop seems to provide even more support.

Interestingly, December 4, 1910, *New York Herald* (1910a) opened its full-page story about Pratt and her toys by referring to a boy who said his mechanical toys play *for* him, not *with* him. And, those advertisements in the 1910 *Evening Telegram* and *Evening World* already quoted above, state:

The “Do-With” Toys Sold Exclusively By Gimbels. *For the little boy who voiced the protest of childhood that toys “just played by themselves” the “Do-With” toys were created, and the child-heart is now delighted with toys which can make play with him.* (Gimble Brothers, 1910a-b; italics added).

Seen in this light, it is remarkable that the *New York Daily Tribune* (1910a) — reprinted in *Christian Science Monitor* (1910) and *Miami Metropolis* (1910), and in summarized form in *Detroit Free Press* (1910) — also assured that Pratt began producing toys after a boy had confessed to her that he was not fond of his mechanical toys because they play *for* him, not *with* him. The following phrase in the *New York Daily Tribune* (1910a) may indicate that Pratt already designed her blocks in 1910, but most probably did not (yet) think they were as important as her dolls and toys.

[Children] who had been brought up on “do-with” toys would build their own houses and barns out of blocks, instead of waiting for their parents to provide them.

Several of the stories about boy Fritz (*e.g.* Pratt, 1914c) describes that he played with a traffic system of trucks, cars and trains just like the boy did in the story about a visit to a friend in Pratt’s autobiography. Does this indicate that these boys are in fact one and the same, and if so, that Pratt had already made blocks especially for him to play with in 1908? This is probably too much speculation; far too much of a good thing.

Education and Art

Abovementioned kindergarten magazine reports show that Pratt first presented her Do-Withs in 1909, while newspaper reports from 1910 about her toys probably indicate she may have already designed prototypes of her blocks in that year — or earlier. Therefore, anecdotes that claim that experimental Hill Floor Blocks (these still were experimental in 1910) inspired Pratt to design blocks herself have no real foundation. Pratt appreciated the play potential the geometric proportions of Hill’s blocks offered when she visited Hill’s kindergarten:

A simple geometrical shape could become any number of things to a child. It could be a truck or a boat or the car of a train. He could build buildings with it from barns to skyscrapers. I could see the children of my as yet unborn school constructing a complete community with blocks. (Pratt, 1948a, p. 29).

This particular section in Pratt’s autobiography does not indicate that Hill’s blocks inspired Pratt to devise blocks of her own — as many wrongly state. Pratt looked at the experimental blocks with a keen professional eye, a carpenter’s eye, yet at the same time also with an educator’s eye, recognizing and acknowledging the play potential of Hill’s blocks.

Pratt’s look was that of an accomplished carpenter of the Arts and Crafts movement who created educational playthings that really ought to be small pieces of art at the same time. Education and art had to be hand and glove. *New York Daily Tribune* (1910a) already hinted that the “inventor of the ‘do-with’ toys” not merely expressed her views on toys, but “views on education and art in the realm of playthings” (compare *Christian Science Monitor*, 1910; *Miami Metropolis*, 1910; *Detroit Free Press*, 1910). That Pratt had both educational and artistic goals with her own toys is already clear in the very first newspaper article about her work in the *Evening Post*.

Caran d’Ache was perhaps the first of the really great artists who devoted himself to toys to the exclusion of everything else after he had become interested in making them, but his creations were

rather more attractive to fellow-artists than they could be to any child. In these new toys [=Do-Withs], on the contrary, there is every appeal to the budding mind, and certain possibilities of play not to be found in the cast-iron objects with which several generations have been forced to content themselves. (*Evening Post*, 1909b; *Washington Herald*, 1909).

The newspaper's referral to Caran d'Ache (pseudonym of French cartoonist and toymaker Emmanuel Poiré, born in Russia) is important. His creations were "playful in style" and "at the same time a work of art" (Curtis, 2018, p. 77). His dolls must have inspired Pratt, indisputably informed as she was by the Arts and Crafts movement.

On Christmas Eve 1911, *Boston Daily Globe* (1911) published an article mainly about toymakers of the Hingham Society of Arts and Crafts. The *Globe's* reporter declared that an "odd little business, that of making handicraft toys, has lately been revived in New England and elsewhere," among others by Caroline Pratt from New York City.

[Complaints] of educators against mechanical and overelaborated toys have been responsible for a New York innovation in playthings — the "Do-with Toys" of Miss Caroline Pratt. Miss Pratt, who has approached this work from the *standpoint of artist and teacher*, has written and lectured about the toy question. (*Italics added*).

Further, an article about the Exhibition of Christmas gifts held at the Teachers College educational museum in 1911, discussed above, also addresses the Arts and Crafts movement in relation to Pratt's Do-Withs: "Miss Pratt's quaint toys, so reminiscent of much of the arts and crafts work..." (*New York Herald*, 1911b). Note, in this respect, that Pratt's first ads concerning her toys appeared in the autumn 1909 numbers of *Craftsman*, the monthly magazine of the American branch of the Arts and Crafts movement (Pratt, 1909a-c).

With all this in view, it is interesting to know that Pratt in 1909, 1910 and 1911, when she was designing and trying to sell her toys and blocks for the first time, was a Craftsman Member of the Society of Arts and Crafts of Boston, Massachusetts (Society of Arts & Crafts, 1910, p. 43; 1911, p. 51; 1912, p. 52). Arts and Crafts were central in all of Pratt's work.

Nevertheless, Do-With™ dolls and toys, despite Pratt's Arts and Crafts enthusiasm, became elements of the past by the end of WWI. In December 1919, Pratt was awarded the Mrs. Hubbard Carpenter Award for toys of greatest art and educational value — a prize of US \$ 25,00 — at the Art Institute of Chicago for her group of wooden dolls (Art Institute of Chicago, 1919, p. 47; 1920, pp. 8-9; *Bulletin of The Art Institute of Chicago*, 1920; see Note 2). Exactly at the moment she received the Award, Pratt closed the Do-With chapter of her life for good. Her beloved 'Do-Withs' had become true art. The irony of history is that as of the same time, Pratt's Unit Blocks — Arts and Crafts artful as these are too — turned out to become important, essential, educational playthings, not only in her own City and Country School, but at many schools, in America, in Europe, in New Zealand, as representants of her educational philosophy. It is the most beautiful Award the blocks received — patented or not.

Notes

1. Edna Smith was born in 1885, Mt. Pleasant, Iowa, and was a 1907 Vassar graduate. Her mother was Selma (Teuscher) Smith, her father the millionaire Captain Charles H. Smith, President and main stockholder of the Western Wheeled Scraper Company, Aurora, Illinois. In November 1910, she succeeded her father on the Board of Directors of the company. At the time she was the owner of stock in the concern valued at more than \$ 300,000. Note that Edna Smith not only co-founded Play School. In 1914, a year after she co-founded Play School, she co-founded the Juvenile Protective Association of Aurora, Illinois. Again a year later she founded Garden School, Carmel, California. She became the secret patron of musician Henry Cowell (1897-1965). In 1921, Smith and Cowell had become engaged. On April 15, 1922, Smith died in a car accident near Lakewood, New Jersey.

Figure 10: Edna Louise Smith (1885-1922), co-founder of the New York City Play School. (Courtesy Mr. Robert Dobyns, www.ednasmith.org.)

2. The author wishes to thank Miss Melanie Emerson, Reference Librarian at the Reyerson Library, The Art Institute of Chicago, for her help in finding referrals to Caroline Pratt in the 1919-1920 Bulletins and in the 1919 Annual Report of the Art Institute of Chicago.

3. Jessie Stanton (1886-1976) — graduated at Barnard College in 1919 — taught at City and Country School for ten years. She has made many block building observations. These observations are kept in the Bank Street College of Education Archives, Record Group 10, Subgroup 2.

Consult also former District Superintendent of Schools Joseph S. Taylor's (1928) article in *New York Sun* for a description of block building in Stanton's class, City and Country School: "In Miss Stanton's class block building is the main project." Stanton explained that a large classroom was needed, that children decided what they would build, and that "the exercise is self-expression and is creative" — this idea originated with Froebel — and that "hundreds and hundreds" of blocks were needed. Later, Stanton (1930) issued *Notes on Block Building Exhibition Shown at the Progressive Education Association Conference — Washington, D.C., 1930*. The booklet contains Stanton's observations of children playing with blocks at the Institute School for Little Children, Vassar Euthenics Institute in Poughkeepsie, New York.

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